

Reversed phase high-performance liquid chromatography for rapid determination of quercetin in flowers of rose species

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Abstract : High-performance liquid chromatography with diode-array detection (HPLC-DAD) has been evaluated for the separation and determination of quercetin in flowers of *R. gallica* and *R. centifolia*. The samples were extracted in 80% methanol by ultrasonic cleaning device for 40 min, and the content of quercetin was analyzed by HPLC under the optimal chromatographic conditions. A Eclipse XDB-C18 column (4.6 mm × 250 mm, 5 μm) was used as the analytical column. The mobile phase was methanol and (pH 4.2) phosphate buffer (v : v = 60 : 40) at a flow rate 0.8 mL/min at 25 °C. The detection wavelength was set at 372 nm to determine the content of quercetin. The results showed linearity over the range of 0.67–100 μg/mL, mean recoveries were in the range of 96.23–100.59% and RSDs was 0.27–0.96% for *R. gallica* and *R. centifolia* respectively.

Keywords : High performance liquid chromatography, diode-array detection, quercetin, *R. gallica*, *R. centifolia*.

Introduction

In many countries, traditional medicines have been and remain the major source of medication for a wide range of ailments. Roses (*Rosa rugosa* Thunb.) are the important ornamental plants and have been referred to as the queen of flowers. Members of the Rosaceae family have long been used for food and medicinal purposes. Its flowers are reported to have astringent, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antidepressant, and diuretic activity and are used in folk medicine as a mild laxative¹⁻⁵. Various terpenes, their glycosides, flavonoids, flavonoid glycosides and anthocyanins have been reported from the flowers of rose⁶⁻⁹. The physiological functions of rose may be partly attributed to their abundance of flavonoids. Flavonoids are a widely distributed group of polyphenolic compounds that have been reported to act as antioxidants in various biological systems. Flavonoids in plants usually occur in a glycosylated form, mainly with glucose or rhamnose, but they can also be linked with galactose,

arabinose, xylose, glucuronic acid or other sugars^{10,11}. Quercetin is one of most abundant natural flavonoids, the applications of quercetin in therapy allergic conditions, including asthma, hayfever, eczema and hives¹². Additional clinical uses include treatment of gout, pancreatitis and prostatitis, which are also, in part, inflammatory conditions¹³. Niu *et al.* confirmed quercetin was the main antioxidant activity ingredients in rose and isolated the quercetin from rose for the first time¹⁴. In addition, Xiaoguang Cao investigated the mechanisms for the effects of quercetin on cultured human RPE cells and in Ccl2/Cx3cr1 double knock-out (DKO) mice, which spontaneously developed progressive retinal lesions mimicking age-related macular degeneration (AMD)¹⁵. Maria Russo reported biochemical and genetic studies on cellular and animal models on the mechanism(s) of action of phytochemicals provided a functional explanation of how and why a diet rich in fruits and vegetables was considered healthy. It was not unusual to find molecules that

protected against diseases, which greatly differed from a physiopathological point of view, such as cancer and cardiovascular disorders¹⁶. Due to the beneficial health effects of quercetin present in rose, simultaneous identification and quantification are very important for many areas of science.

A few reports are available on the characterization of quercetin by HPLC techniques on different rose species¹⁷⁻²⁰. However, there is no method for simultaneous identification and quantification quercetin in flowers of *R. gallica* and *R. centifolia*. In this study, we report here the rapid determination of quercetin in rose samples, which also provides a quantitative analysis of quercetin for other traditional medicines.

Results and discussion

Optimization of the chromatographic conditions :

To enhance the resolution, restrain the ionization, and inhibit the tailing and broadening of the peak in the whole process of separation for quercetin, several mobile phases consisting of mixtures of MeOH and ACN as an organic

modifier in different ratios with phosphate buffer and water were surveyed using authentic compounds. Meanwhile, one serious problem in the separation of quercetin was peak tailing, which had been connected with dissociation of the hydroxyl groups. The presence of acid in a mobile phase could prevent this effect by changing the pH, thereby improving peak symmetry of analyte^{21,22}. In the study, when the pH 4.2, the problem of peak tailing was eliminated.

ACN/H₂O mixtures in different proportions did not enable an acceptable separation for the time being long (50–60 min) and the peak of quercetin being poor. When different proportions of MeOH/phosphoric acid were used as mobile phase instead of ACN/H₂O, the results showed that quercetin peaks eluted at 15–16 min and the peak shape was good in Fig. 1. Eventually, a mobile phase consisting of MeOH as eluent A and (pH 4.2) phosphate buffer as eluent B (A : B, 60 : 40 v/v) was selected to achieve high sensitivity and good peak shape. Fig. 2 showed the chromatogram of *R. gallica* sample under the optimal chromatographic conditions.

Fig. 1. The chromatogram of the standard solution of quercetin.

Fig. 2. The chromatogram of *R. gallica* sample.

The standard solution of quercetin was analyzed under the optimal chromatographic conditions in order to get the best response, quercetin showed three characteristic absorbance peaks at 211 nm, 253 nm and 372 nm by UV spectra scanned between 200 and 600 nm in Fig. 3, but there were lower sensitivities at 211 nm, 253 nm than at 372 nm, the suitable characteristic absorbance wavelength was approximately at 372 nm for quercetin. Therefore, the detection wavelength was set at 372 nm in this method.

Fig. 3. The UV absorbance spectra of quercetin at 200–600 nm.

Method validation :

Regression equation ($Y = 929256X - 418250$) and coefficient of correlation ($r = 0.9992$) revealed a good linearity response for developed method in Table 1, which indicated that the proposed method exhibited a good sensitivity for the quantification of quercetin. The LOD for quercetin was 0.18 µg/mL and the LOQ for quercetin was found to be 0.58 µg/mL, respectively. The linear range of this assay extended from 0.67 to 100 µg/mL for quercetin. 8.00 µg/mL quercetin was repeatedly injected into HPLC at 4 h intervals over 24 h under the same chromatographic conditions. The relative standard deviation (RSD) showed that the determination method was

stable over 24 h ($RSD \leq 0.98\%$). The determination of peak areas repeatability experiments indicated the method was repeatable in Table 2. The inter-day precision values (expressed in terms of % RSD) were observed in Table 3, RSD demonstrated the good precision of the proposed method. The accuracy of the proposed method was expressed as the recover of quercetin standard material added to the pre-analyzed sample in Table 4. The mean recoveries and RSDs were found to be in the range of 96.23–100.59% and 0.27–0.96% for *R. gallica* and *R. centifolia*,

respectively. The results showed that the recovery of this method was accurate.

Determination the content of quercetin :

The validated method was applied for determination of quercetin in the flowers of *R. gallica* and *R. centifolia* according to the same retention time and UV absorbance spectra of standard materials and samples. Six parallel samples were analyzed. The results were shown in Table 5, the content of quercetin in the flowers of *R. centifolia* (8.02 µg/g) was higher than that in the flowers of *R. gallica* (7.25 µg/g). Neeraj Kumar *et al.* determined the polyphenols in flowers of rose species, the content of

Table 1. Linearity and detection limits for the quercetin

Compd.	Linearity (µg/mL)	Regression equation ^a	Correlation coefficient (r ²)	LOD (µg/mL)	LOQ (µg/mL)
Quercetin	0.67–100	$Y = 929256X - 418250$	0.9992	0.38	1.14

*Y = Peak area, X = concentration of quercetin (µg/mL).

Table 2. The assessment of determination method repeatability at different times (n = 6)

Detecting time	0	4	8	12	16	20	24
Peak area	21398865	21397253	21398823	21399010	21398872	21397842	21397109
RSD (%)	0.98	0.81	0.49	0.29	0.97	0.38	0.92

Table 3. Inter-day precision values for the analyte ($n = 6$, mean)

Compd.	Day 1		Day 2		Day 3	
	t_R	RSD	t_R	RSD	t_R	RSD
	(min)	(%)	(min)	(%)	(min)	(%)
Quercetin	15.44	0.79	15.45	0.92	15.45	0.86

^aThe concentration of quercetin was 8.00 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

Table 4. Results of accuracy experiment ($n = 6$)

Sample	Blank	Added	Detected	Mean recoveries	RSD
	($\mu\text{g/mg}$)	($\mu\text{g/mg}$)	(%)	(%)	(%)
<i>R. gallica</i>	2.17	1.73	1.650	98.26	0.88
	2.17	2.17	1.652	100.59	0.27
	2.17	4.77	1.653	97.54	0.76
<i>R. centifolia</i>	2.40	1.92	1.701	96.23	0.68
	2.40	4.80	1.664	98.25	0.96
	2.40	5.28	1.649	97.64	0.82

Table 5. Detection results of quercetin ($n = 6$)

Sample	1	2	3	4	5	6	Mean value
<i>R. gallica</i> ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	7.19	7.32	7.23	7.27	7.34	7.15	7.25
<i>R. centifolia</i> ($\mu\text{g/g}$)	8.10	7.95	7.98	8.09	8.06	7.94	8.02

quercetin was 86.87 and 80.41 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for *R. brunonii* and *R. bourboniana*, respectively¹³. Ghasem Haghi and Alireza Hatami determined flavonoids in plant materials, the result showed the content of quercetin in *R. damascena* flower was 11.1 $\mu\text{g/g}$ ¹⁷. The content of quercetin was different in different flowers of rose species.

Experimental

Instruments :

A Thermo-Finnigan Surveyor High Performance Liquid Chromatography with diode-array detection (Thermo Finnigan, MA, USA). RE-52AA Rotary Evaporator (Shanghai Yarong Biochemical Co., Ltd., China). pH measurements of the mobile phase were done by using a digital type pH meter (Mettler Toledo, S20 SevenEasy, Columbia, USA). KW5200 ultrasonic cleaning device (Kun Shan Ultrasonic Instruments Co., Ltd., China).

Chemicals :

Methanol (HPLC grade, Tianjin Kermel Reagent Co., Ltd., Tianjin, China). Phosphoric acid, sodium dihydrogen phosphate, sodium hydrogen phosphate (Analytical grade, Sinopharm Chemical Reagent Beijing Co., Ltd., Beijing, China). Quercetin standard material (HPLC grade, Chengdu Scholar Bio-Tech. Co., Ltd., Sichuan, China).

All the water was obtained from an Ultra-pure Water System (SG Ultra Clear System, Wasseraufbereitung und Regenerierstation GmbH, Germany).

Materials :

Flowers of *R. gallica* and *R. centifolia* (Pingyin, Shandong, China) were bought in the pharmacy of Xinxiang City, which was identified by the Chinese Medicine Laboratory of the College of Pharmacy of Xinxiang Medical University.

Standard stock solution preparation :

Standard stock solution was freshly prepared within the range of 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ by dissolving 0.0050 g quercetin standard material in 25.0 mL mobile phase.

Sample preparation :

3.00 g of *R. gallica* and *R. centifolia* were weighed and taken in a conical flask with stopper. 100 mL of 80% ethanol was added to it and soaked for 24 h. Ultrasonic extraction was carried out for 40 min, and the solution was filtrated and then defatted with petroleum ether by rotary evaporator at 60 °C concentrated to 10 mL, the sample solution concentrated was filtered through 0.45 μm microporous membrane, cold storage backup for measurement.

Chromatographic conditions :

A Eclipse XDB-C18 column (250 mm \times 4.6 mm, 5 μm) was used for the separation of quercetin from samples. The column was maintained at 25 °C throughout the analytic process and the eluant was monitored at 370 nm. The mobile phase was methanol and phosphate buffer (60 : 40, v/v) (pH 4.2) at a flow rate of 0.8 mL/min. The injection volume was 20 μL .

Calibration curve :

To establish calibration curve, 0.00, 0.50, 1.00, 2.00, 4.00, and 8.00 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ quercetin working standard solutions were made by gradual dilution standard stock solution with the mobile phase, respectively. The calibration curve was constructed by plotting the peak areas versus the concentration of analyte ($\mu\text{g/mL}$).

Limit of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ) :

The sensibility of the method evaluated determining the limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ). The LOD is the smallest quantity of analyte that can be shown to be significantly greater than the mea-

surement (random) error of the blank at the prescribed level of confidence (usually 95%). It is the lowest concentration of analyte in a sample that can be detected but not necessarily quantified, and it is calculated as 3 times the standard deviation (SD) of the background noise. The LOQ is the smallest amount of analyte in a test sample that can be quantitatively determined with suitable precision and accuracy under previously established method and conditions. It was taken as 10 times the SD of the background noise¹⁸.

Stability study :

8.00 µg/mL of the standard solution was repeatedly injected into HPLC at 4 h intervals over 24 h after the extraction.

Repeatability experiment :

Measurements of inter-day variability were utilized to assess the repeatability of the developed method. The RSD was assessed by analyzing 8.00 µg/mL of the standard solution on three consecutive days (two parallel samples each day).

Accuracy experiment :

Accuracy (expressed as recovery) for the quercetin characterized in the extracts was determined by spiking the samples with a known amount of quercetin standard material before extraction. The standard solution was added to samples at three different contents, and average recovery was measured in triplicate.

Conclusions :

A simple, rapid, and reliable method for determination of quercetin in rose species was presented. A content of quercetin was analyzed by HPLC. The developed method has been satisfactorily verified for its accuracy and selectivity and can be used for quality control of herbal formulations containing quercetin.

References

1. R. Leenen, A. J. C. Roodenburg, L. B. M. Tijburg and S. A. Wiseman, *Eur. J. Clin. Nutr.*, 2000, **54**, 87.
2. T. B. Ng, F. Liu and Z. T. Wang, *Life Sci.*, 2000, **66**, 709.
3. W. Ren, Z. Qiao, H. Wang, L. Zhu and L. Zhang, *Med. Res. Rev.*, 2003, **23**, 519.
4. V. Singh, V. K. Kaul, B. Singh and R. P. Sood, in : S. S. Handa, M. K. Kaul, Regional Research Laboratory, Jammu Tawi, India, 1997, 195.
5. A. J. J. Dugas, J. Castaneda-Acosta, G. C. Bonin, K. L. Price, N. H. Fischer and G. W. Winston, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 2000, **63**, 327.
6. N. Oka, A. Ikegami, M. Ohki, K. Sakata, A. Yagi and N. Watanabe, *Phytochemistry*, 1998, **47**, 1527.
7. H. Knapp, M. Straubinger, S. Fornari, N. Oka and N. Watanabe, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 1998, **46**, 1966.
8. A. Shieber, K. Mihalev, N. Berardini, P. Mollov and R. Carle, *J. Biosci.*, 2005, **60**, 379.
9. M. Saito, H. Hoyosama, T. Ariga, S. Kataoka and N. Yamaji, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 1998, **46**, 1460.
10. A. D. L. R. Laura, A. P. Emilio and A. G. A. Gustavo, "Fruit and Vegetable Phytochemicals : Chemistry, Nutritional Value and Stability", Wiley-Blackwell, Oxford, 2010, p. 53.
11. H. M. Merken and G. R. Beecher, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 2000, **48**, 577.
12. K. V. Hirpara, P. Aggarwal, A. J. Mukherjee, N. Joshi and A. C. Burman, *Anti-Cancer Agents in Medicinal Chemistry*, 2009, **9**, 138.
13. T. L. Vaughan, *NC State Theses and Dissertations*, 2003, 4.
14. S. M. Niu, W. Li, L. Li, L. S. Shi, G. Bai and F. Liu, *Acta Scientiarum. Naturalium. UN*, 2006, **39**, 91.
15. X. Cao, M. Liu, J. Tuo, D. Shen and C. Chan, *Exp. Eye Res.*, 2010, **91**, 15.
16. M. Russo, C. Spagnuolo, I. Tedesco, S. Bilotto and G. L. Russo, *Biochem. Pharm.*, 2012, **83**, 6.
17. K. Neeraj, B. Pamita, S. Bikram, G. Ajai P. and K. K. Vijay, *J. Sep. Sci.*, 2008, **31**, 262.
18. O. Monika, *J. Pharmaceut. Biomed.*, 2008, **48**, 629.
19. H. Ghasem and H. Alireza, *J. Agric. Food Chem.*, 2010, **58**, 10812.
20. E. M. Jovel, X. L. Zhou, D. S. Ming, T. R. Wahbe and G. H. N. Towers, *Can. J. Physiol. Pharmacol.*, 2007, **85**, 865.
21. A. Hasler, O. Sticher and B. Meier, *J. Chromatogr.*, 1990, **508**, 236.
22. Y. Zu, C. Li, Y. Fu and C. Zhao, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal.*, 2006, **41**, 714.

